

**AN
INTERNSHIP REPORT
ON
EXPENSE TRACKER MANAGEMENT SYSTEM
PROJECT
BY
KAMAL ACHARYA
(Tribhuvan University)**

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CHAPTER 1

PROJECT DESCRIPTION

1.1 INTRODUCTION

We are developing an php application named as “Expense Tracker” and this application is used to manage the application user’s daily expenses in a more efficient and manageable way. By using this application we can reduce the manual calculations for their daily expenses and keep the track of the expenditure. In this application, user can provide his income to calculate his total expenses per day and these results will stored for unique user. This application has many limitations which can be overcome in future. The main purpose of this application is to track all the expenses made by a user. The user can generate report of his expenses based on the transaction date of the expenses or category of items. This application will be deployed on separate web server and application server. And for load balancing, it will be deployed on two web servers and application servers. This Expense Tracker application falls in the Finance Category and serves the important purpose of managing finances which is a very important part of one’s life. The software product went through the design, development, and the testing phase as a part of the Software Development Lifecycle. The application’s interface is designed using custom art elements, the functionality is implemented using php, and the phase of testing the product was accomplished successfully. The application is not much user intensive but just comprises of having them enter the expense amount, date, category, merchant and other optional attributes (taking picture of the receipts, entering notes about the expense, adding subcategories to the categories). With this entered information, the user is able to see the expense details daily, weekly, monthly, and yearly in figures, graphs, PDF format, and can print them as well if a printer is detected or scanned nearby. All these topics have been explained in detail in their respective chapters. The aim of this is to provide a solution for this application users on how to manage finances in any circumstance by keeping track of their expenses every day. Ultimately, this contributes to societal well-being. Expense tracker is complete to track your all the expenses bared by your pocket or based by you & manage your personal finance. So that you can trace where your money goes as well as from where money comes in, you can limit & plan accordingly. A feature rich tracking application with numerous powerful tools like, Income/Expense, Bills, Accounts, Reports etc. Not only

that, app has all the information yet not un-secure as it does not ask to save any sensitive data for its operations. Budgeting is an integral part of the society. Budget Tracking involves recording and analyzing the incomes and expenses of a person or an organization over a particular period of time. Today, since we are living in a hurry up and get it done society, many people are looking forward to efficient ways to budget their time and money. During the recent years, some research has been carried out on household budget .It has been noted that in most cases, budget management is being done mentally and never being put on paper which makes Expense Tracking very difficult. This is probably due to the fact that many people do not know how to do it or do not have an appropriate means that will do Expense Tracking and Analysis for them. Budgeting also requires us to look ahead and formalize future goals. By establish a budget, people can set goals for achieving a certain level of income and monitor their expenses. Many home based and small-business owners have observed that their increase in profit margins did not occur until they had a written revenue goal and a method with which to monitor expenses .Expense Tracking is important because it helps us to keep track of our expenditures based on the incomes made. It also allows us to plan for future projects and expenditures. Being able to Analyze and compare income and expenses over a period of time, by calculating monthly/yearly profit's and expenses as well as deviations, help us to take important decisions. Bankruptcy and future budgets can also be predicted via the data fed during expense tracking.

1.2 EXISTING SYSTEM:

If we want to balance a income and expense for each month we have to do it manually but we can't do this for each and every month those who have a lot of income and expenses, so to reduce the stress for the person and make easy to calculate the income and expense, this php application has been so much helpful for a person to avoid the manual way calculating his income and expenses. In this application we have features like add expenses categories add income so that we can add what are the income and expenses has been done for a month. But it can used to perform calculation on income and expenses to overcome this problem we propose the new application.

DRAW BACKS:

- Experienced manager may attempt to introduce budgetary slack.
- The time requirement can be unusually large if there is a participative budgeting process in place, since such a system involves an unusually large number of employees.
- The expense may prescribe that certain amounts of overhead costs be allocated to various departments.
- Time required. It can be very time-consuming to create a budget.

1.3 PROPOSED SYSTEM:

In this php application we are going to develop this by adding some extra features. In expenses we have some expense feature like add expenses we can add new expense for a month, add categories , export expenses (it will remain as a specific date how much expense has taken for a month), remove export files (it will remove the remainder for the month), view expenses (we can view what are all expense for a month). In income tracker some of the features like add income, add category, categories, export income, remove export files, and view expenses. In add income (we can add new income for a month), add categories (we can add new categories for a month), export income (it will remind us in a date what we have given i.e. from date and to date), remove export files (it will remove the remainder what we have given to remind). By adding these features it helps the users to work more efficient and in an effective manner. This eliminates the drawback of the existing system application.

ADVANTAGES

- Add expense (we can add new expense for a month)
- Add categories (we can add new categories for a month)
- Export income (it will remind us in a date what we have given i.e. from date and to date)
- Remove export files (it will remove the remainder what we have given to remind).

1.3.1 HARDWARE SPECIFICATION

- Processor : Dual core processor 2.6.0 GHz
- RAM : 1GB
- Hard disk : 160 GB
- Compact Disk : 650 MB
- Keyboard : Standard keyboard
- Monitor : 15 inch color monitor

1.3.2 SOFTWARE SPECIFICATION

- Front End : PHP
- IDE : dream weaver
- Back End : My SQL

1.3.3 PHP

PHP is server side back end programming language. It executes in server along with maximum all available web servers like Apache, IIS (Internet Information Server) etc., and return the response as required MIME type. It is a Pre Process Hypertext, we could do many things on server by using PHP on server and co-ordinate with DB server for CURD (Create, Update, Read, and Delete) actions. Front end in the seance, UI which intact the users, it can done by HTML, or any others. And UI Behavior is defined in UI back end Languages (Scripting languages) via: Java script, VB script

PHP started out as a small open source project that evolved as more and more people found out how useful it was. Rasmus Lerdorf unleashed the first version of PHP way back in 1994.

- PHP is a recursive acronym for "PHP: Hypertext Preprocessor".
- PHP is a server side scripting language that is embedded in HTML. It is used to manage dynamic content, databases, session tracking, even build entire e-commerce sites.
- It is integrated with a number of popular databases, including MySQL, PostgreSQL, Oracle, Sybase, Informix, and Microsoft SQL Server.

- PHP is pleasingly zippy in its execution, especially when compiled as an Apache module on the UNIX side. The MySQL server, once started, executes even very complex queries with huge result sets in record-setting time.
- PHP supports a large number of major protocols such as POP3, IMAP, and LDAP. PHP4 added support for Java and distributed object architectures (COM and CORBA), making n-tier development a possibility for the first time.
- PHP is forgiving: PHP language tries to be as forgiving as possible.
- PHP Syntax is C-Like.

Common Uses of PHP

PHP performs system functions, i.e. from files on a system it can create, open, read, write and close them. The other uses of PHP are:

PHP can handle forms, i.e. gather data from files, save data to a file, thru email you can send data, return data to the user. You add, delete and modify elements within your database thru PHP. Access cookies variables and set cookies. Using PHP, you can restrict users to access some pages of your website. It can encrypt data.

Characteristics of PHP

Five important characteristics make PHP's practical nature possible:

- Simplicity
- Efficiency
- Security
- Flexibility
- Familiarity

PHP Variables

The main way to store information in the middle of a PHP program is by using a variable. Here are the most important things to know about variables in PHP.

- All variables in PHP are denoted with a leading dollar sign (\$).
- The value of a variable is the value of its most recent assignment.

- Variables are assigned with the = operator, with the variable on the left-hand side and the expression to be evaluated on the right.
- Variables can, but do not need, to be declared before assignment.
- Variables in PHP do not have intrinsic types - a variable does not know in advance whether it will be used to store a number or a string of characters.
- Variables used before they are assigned have default values.
- PHP does a good job of automatically converting types from one to another when necessary.

PHP variables are Perl-like. PHP has a total of eight data types which we use to construct our variables:

- **Integers:** are whole numbers, without a decimal point, like 4195.
- **Doubles:** are floating-point numbers, like 3.14159 or 49.1.
- **Booleans:** have only two possible values either true or false.
- **NULL:** is a special type that only has one value: NULL.
- **Strings:** are sequences of characters, like 'PHP supports string operations.'
- **Arrays:** are named and indexed collections of other values.
- **Objects:** are instances of programmer-defined classes, which can package up both other kinds of values and functions that are specific to the class.
- **Resources:** are special variables that hold references to resources external to PHP (such as database connections).

Back End (MySQL)

MySQL is the world's most used open source relational database management system (RDBMS) as of 2008 that run as a server providing multi-user access to a number of databases. The MySQL development project has made its source code available under the terms of the GNU General Public License, as well as under a variety of proprietary agreements. MySQL was owned and sponsored by a single for-profit firm, the Swedish company MySQL AB, now owned by Oracle Corporation.

MySQL is a popular choice of database for use in web applications, and is a central component of the widely used LAMP open source web application software stack—LAMP is an

acronym for "Linux, Apache, MySQL, Perl/PHP/Python." Free-software-open source projects that require a full-featured database management system often use MySQL.

For commercial use, several paid editions are available, and offer additional functionality. Applications which use MySQL databases include: TYPO3, Joomla, Word Press, phpBB, MyBB, Drupal and other software built on the LAMP software stack. MySQL is also used in many high-profile, large-scale World Wide Web products, including Wikipedia, Google (though not for searches), ImagebookTwitter, Flickr, Nokia.com, and YouTube.

Inter images

MySQL is primarily an RDBMS and ships with no GUI tools to administer MySQL databases or manage data contained within the databases. Users may use the included command line tools, or use MySQL "front-ends", desktop software and web applications that create and manage MySQL databases, build database structures, back up data, inspect status, and work with data records. The official set of MySQL front-end tools, MySQL Workbench is actively developed by Oracle, and is freely available for use.

Graphical

The official MySQL Workbench is a free integrated environment developed by MySQL AB, which enables users to graphically administer MySQL databases and visually design database structures. MySQL Workbench replaces the previous package of software, MySQL GUI Tools. Similar to other third-party packages, but still considered the authoritative MySQL frontend, MySQL Workbench lets users manage database design & modeling, SQL development (replacing MySQL Query Browser) and Database administration (replacing MySQL Administrator).MySQL Workbench is available in two editions, the regular free and open source Community Edition which may be downloaded from the MySQL website, and the proprietary Standard Edition which extends and improves the feature set of the Community Edition.

MySQL ships with some command line tools. Third-parties have also developed tools to manage a MySQL server, some listed below. Maatkit - a cross-platform toolkit for MySQL, PostgreSQL and Memcached, developed in Perl Maatkit can be used to prove replication is

working correctly, fix corrupted data, automate repetitive tasks, and speed up servers. Maatkit is included with several GNU/Linux distributions such as CentOS and Debian and packages are available for Programming. MySQL works on many different system platforms, including AIX, BSDi, FreeBSD, HP-UX, eComStation, i5/OS, IRIX, Linux, Mac OS X, Microsoft Windows, NetBSD, Novell NetWare, OpenBSD, OpenSolaris, OS/2 Warp, QNX, Solaris, Symbian, SunOS, SCO Open Server, SCO UnixWare, Sanos and Tru64. A port of MySQL to OpenVMS also exists. MySQL is written in C and C++. Its SQL parser is written in yacc, and a home-brewed lexical analyzer. Many programming languages with language-specific APIs include libraries for accessing MySQL databases. These include MySQL Connector/Net for integration with Microsoft's Visual Studio (languages such as C# and VB are most commonly used) and the JDBC driver for Java. In addition, an ODBC interimage called MyODBC allows additional programming languages that support the ODBC inter image to communicate with a MySQL database, such as ASP or ColdFusion. The HTSQL - URL-based query method also ships with a MySQL adapter, allowing direct interaction between a MySQL database and any web client via structured URLs.

Features

As of April 2009, MySQL offered MySQL 5.1 in two different variants: the open source MySQL Community Server and the commercial Enterprise Server. MySQL 5.5 is offered under the same licenses. They have a common code base and include the following features:

A broad subset of ANSI SQL 99, as well as extensions

- Cross-platform support
- Stored procedures
- Triggers
- Cursors
- Updatable Views
- Information schema

Strict mode (ensures MySQL does not truncate or otherwise modify data to conform to an underlying data type, when an incompatible value is inserted into that type)

X/Open XAdistributed transaction processing (DTP) support; two phase commit as part of this, using Oracle's InnoDB engine

- Transactions with the InnoDB, and Cluster storage engines
- SSL support
- Query caching
- Sub-SELECTs (i.e. nested SELECTs)
- Replication support (i.e. Master-Master Replication & Master-Slave Replication)
- Embedded database library
- Partitioned tables with pruning of partitions in optimizer
- Shared-nothing clustering through MySQL Cluster
- Hot backup (via mysqlhotcopy) under certain conditions

Multiple storage engines, allowing one to choose the one that is most effective for each table in the application (in MySQL 5.0, storage engines must be compiled in; in MySQL 5.1, storage engines can be dynamically loaded at run time): Native storage engines (MyISAM, Falcon, Merge, Memory (heap), Federated, Archive, CSV, Black hole, Cluster, EXAMPLE, Maria, and InnoDB, which was made the default as of 5.5). Partner-developed storage engines (solidDB, NitroEDB, ScaleDB, TokuDB, Infobright (formerly Brighthouse), Kickfire, XtraDB, IBM DB2). InnoDB used to be a partner-developed storage engine, but with recent acquisitions, Oracle now owns both MySQL core and InnoDB.

CHAPTER 2

LOGICAL DEVELOPMENT

2.1. DFDs

A two-dimensional diagram explains how data is processed and transferred in a system. The graphical depiction identifies each source of data and how it interacts with other data sources to reach a common output. Individuals seeking to draft a data flow diagram must identify external inputs and outputs, determine how the inputs and outputs relate to each other, and explain with graphics how these connections relate and what they result in. This type of diagram helps business development and design teams visualize how data is processed and identify or improve certain aspects.

Data flow Symbols:

Symbol	Description
	An entity . A source of data or a destination for data.
	A process or task that is performed by the system.
	A data store , a place where data is held between processes.
	A data flow .

LEVEL 0

DFD Level 0 is also called a Context Diagram. It's a basic overview of the whole system or process being analyzed or modeled. It's designed to be an at-a-glance view, showing the system as a single high-level process, with its relationship to external entities. It should be easily understood by a wide audience, including stakeholders, business analysts, data analysts and developers. A context diagram gives an overview and it is the highest level in a data flow diagram, containing only one process representing the entire system. It should be split into major processes which give greater detail and each major process may further split to give more detail.

Level 0 DFD must balance with the context diagram it describes. Input going into a process is different from outputs leaving the process. Data stores are first shown at this level.

Fig 2.1.1 level 0-DFD

LEVEL 1

DFD Level 1 provides a more detailed breakout of pieces of the Context Level Diagram. You will highlight the main functions carried out by the system, as you break down the high-level process of the Context Diagram into its sub – processes. Level 1 - interaction between 2 different business applications. This is primarily used to explain the process to business and tech leads, QA leads. As described previously, context diagrams (level 0 DFDs) are diagrams where the whole system is represented as a single process. A level 1 DFD notates each of the main sub-processes that together form the complete system. We can think of a level 1 DFD as an “exploded view” of the context diagram.

Fig 2.1.2 level 1 DFD

2.2 ARCHITECTURAL DESIGN

A system architecture or systems architecture is the conceptual model that defines the structure, behavior, and more views of a system. An architecture description is a formal description and representation of a system, organized in a way that supports reasoning about the structures and behaviors of the system. System architecture can comprise system components, the externally visible properties of those components, the relationships (e.g. the behavior) between them. It can provide a plan from which products can be procured, and systems developed, that will work together to implement the overall system. There have been efforts to formalize languages to describe system architecture; collectively these are called architecture description languages (ADLs).

Fig 2.2 architecture diagram

Various organizations define systems architecture in different ways, including:

- An allocated arrangement of physical elements which provides the design solution for a consumer product or life-cycle process intended to satisfy the requirements of the functional architecture and the requirements baseline.
- Architecture comprises the most important, pervasive, top-level, strategic inventions, decisions, and their associated rationales about the overall structure (i.e., essential elements and their relationships) and associated characteristics and behavior.
- If documented, it may include information such as a detailed inventory of current hardware, software and networking capabilities; a description of long-range plans and priorities for future purchases, and a plan for upgrading and/or replacing dated equipment and software.

- An architecture diagram is a graphical representation of a set of concepts that are part of architecture, including their principles, elements and components. Architecture diagram can help system designers and developers visualize the high-level, overall structure of their system or application, in order to ensure the system meets their users' needs. Using architecture diagram, you can also describe patterns that are used throughout the design. It's somewhat like a blueprint that you use as a guide, so that you and your colleagues can discuss, improve and follow.

ASSUMPTIONS

Before developing the application, we have made following assumptions,

1. One user can have only one account.
2. One category can have many items.
3. Each user can define his own category list.
4. When a user opens an Account the first time, the balance will be zero.
5. In current implementation of this project one transaction contains only one item but the structure that we provide is enabling us to do further extension if we want to apply one transaction contains many items. For the sake of simplicity and the time constraint we decided to implement the current condition.
6. User can generate the expense report based on the transaction date or category type.

CHAPTER 3

DATABASE DESIGN

After discussing with other groups, we came up with following database schema. We agreed with the schema of separating items with transaction because we want to keep track of the items. Our team tried to make specific categorization for specific user so user can name his own categories, as he likes.

3.1. DATA DICTIONARY

Table structure for table user_category

Field	Type	Null	Default
id	int(10)	Yes	NULL
user	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL
category	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL

3.1.1 Table design

Dumping data for table user_category

1	acharyak182@gmail.com	Food
2	acharyak182@gmail.com	Education
3	acharyak182@gmail.com	Transport
4	acharyak182@gmail.com	Medical
5	acharyak182@gmail.com	Grocery
6	acharyak182@gmail.com	entertainment

Table structure for table user_details

Field	Type	Null	Default
id	int(100)	Yes	NULL
name	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL
contact	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL
email	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL
address	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL
password	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL
rdate	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL

Dumping data for table user_details

1	Kamal	7339333830	acharyak182@gmail.com	trichy	123	01-11-19
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Table structure for table user_expense

Field	Type	Null	Default
id	int(10)	Yes	NULL
user	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL
month	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL
cdate	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL
category	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL
amount	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL
status	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL

Dumping data for table user_expense

1	acharyak182@gmail.com	11	01	food	100	0
2	acharyak182@gmail.com	11	01	transport	100	0

Table structure for table user_income

Field	Type	Null	Default
id	int(10)	Yes	NULL
user	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL
amount	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL
month	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL

Dumping data for table user_income

1	acharyak182@gmail.com	10000	11
2	acharyak182@gmail.com	5000	10

3.3 RELATIONSHIP DIAGRAM

Entity Relationship Diagram, also known as ERD, ER Diagram or ER model, is a type of structural diagram for use in database design. An ERD contains different symbols and connectors that visualize two important information: The major entities within the system scope, and the inter-relationships among these entities. And that's why it's called "Entity" "Relationship" diagram (ERD)!When we talk about entities in ERD, very often we are referring to business objects such as people/role (e.g. Student), tangible business objects (e.g. Product), intangible business objects (e.g. Log), etc. "Relationship" is about how these entities relate to each other within the system.

Fig 3.3.1ER diagram

CHAPTER 4

PROGRAM DESIGN

4.1MODULES

➤ USER

4.1.1 USER MODULE

- **Registration:** The user has to register into the system providing his personal details. The user will enter their individual details to be a user in the developed php application. Thus while registering they can also get the username and password for login session.
- **Login:** The user has to login into the system to add or view the expenses details, the user is remembered once he logs in until he logs out saving his time to login every time.
- **Add Expenses:** The user is allowed to add expenses refer to also adding a picture related to the details. The user can add picture or leaves empty without adding picture. Thus it helps the user to describe the event they are posting.
- **View Expenses:** The user can view the expenses details the user has been selected from the admin. The expenses details can't be viewed by everyone which are in public. Thus the expenses transaction details will be blocked if the user feels uncomfortable.
- **Added List:** User can also view the list of expenses added by him and action taken by admin if any. The list can be viewed by the user which they posted in public. If they wish to delete they can delete it

CHAPTER 5

TESTING

5.1 SYSTEM TESTING

System Testing is the testing of a complete and fully integrated software product. Usually, software is only one element of a larger computer-based system. Ultimately, software is interfaced with other software/hardware systems. System Testing is actually a series of different tests whose sole purpose is to exercise the full computer-based system.

Two Category of System Testing

- **Black Box Testing**
- **White Box Testing**

System test falls under the black box testing category of software testing.

- White box testing is the testing of the internal workings or code of a software application. In contrast,
- Black box or System Testing is the opposite. System test involves the external workings of the software from the user's perspective.

System Testing involves testing the software code for following

- Testing the fully integrated applications including external peripherals in order to check how components interact with one another and with the system as a whole. This is also called End to End testing scenario.
- Verify thorough testing of every input in the application to check for desired outputs.
- Testing of the user's experience with the application. That is a very basic description of what is involved in system testing. You need to build detailed test cases and test suites that test each aspect of the application as seen from the outside without looking at the actual source code.

These are the steps taken to fully test new software in preparation for marketing it:

- **Unit testing** - testing performed on each module or block of code during development. Unit Testing is normally done by the programmer who writes the code.
- **Integration testing** - testing done before, during and after integration of a new module into the main software package. This involves testing of each individual code module. One piece of software can contain several modules which are often created by several different programmers. It is crucial to test each module's effect on the entire program model.
- **System testing** - testing done by a professional testing agent on the completed software product before it is introduced to the market.
- **Acceptance testing** - beta testing of the product done by the actual end users.

CHAPTER 6

CONCLUSION

We now present and discuss the limitations of the new product, issues faced, and the remedies to those limitations. While building this expense tracking software project, the major focus was to make this tool less user intensive and more user productive. It could have been used in other countries if I would have used currency converters in the php application, which I will improvise in the later version. Certain issues were faced while implementing this tool and various important things were kept in mind. For example, the user interface is designed simple yet creative so that the user doesn't face any difficulty in using the php software application and the expense data is persisted on the device even if the user deletes the application from the memory background. Core Data was chosen over SQLite to persist the data which is very beneficial even though the data would reside on the device locally the application is designed in such a simple and straight forward manner that the user faces no problems or difficulties in using this software tool to track the expenses. The user can only enter the expense/income amount in Currency. The application could have been more user friendly. For example – if the user keeps track of the daily expenses and spends money at Starbucks every day, he has to enter all the information amount etc. himself all over again. Searching functionality is missing in the current version of the application. Suppose the user wants to search and see the expenses made for a particular category say “Food - Starbucks” for the past 3 months, the user has to scroll through the calendar provided and see it. The reports in terms of graphs show a comparison of the expenses/incomes separately made on different categories. But the graph report doesn't show or evaluate income made v/s expense.

CHAPTER 7

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CHAPTER 8

APPENDIX

8.1 SOURCE CODE

```
<?php
$connect=mysql_connect("localhost","root","");
mysql_select_db("expense_tracker",$connect);
?>
<?php
include("dbconnect.php");
session_start();
extract($_POST);
if(isset($_POST['btn']))
{
echo $qry=mysql_query("select * from user_details where email='$email' and password='$pass'");
$num=mysql_num_rows($qry);
    if($num==1)
    {
        $_SESSION['email']=$email;
    ?>
        <script language="javascript">
        alert("Login Successfully");
        window.location.href="user_home.php";
        </script>
    <?php
    }
else
    {
    ?>
        <script language="javascript">
        alert("Failed");
        window.location.href="index.php";
```

```

        </script>
        <?php
    }

}
?>
<!DOCTYPE HTML>
<html>
<head>
<title>Easy Admin Panel an Admin Panel Category Flat Bootstrap Responsive Website Template | Sign In
:: w3layouts</title>
<meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1">
<meta http-equiv="Content-Type" content="text/html; charset=utf-8" />
<meta name="keywords" content="Easy Admin Panel Responsive web template, Bootstrap Web
Templates, Flat Web Templates, Android Compatible web template,
Smartphone Compatible web template, free webdesigns for Nokia, Samsung, LG, SonyEricsson, Motorola
web design" />
<script type="application/x-javascript"> addEventListener("load", function() { setTimeout(hideURLbar,
0); }, false); function hideURLbar(){ window.scrollTo(0,1); } </script>
<!-- Bootstrap Core CSS -->
<link href="css/bootstrap.min.css" rel='stylesheet' type='text/css' />
<!-- Custom CSS -->
<link href="css/style.css" rel='stylesheet' type='text/css' />
<!-- Graph CSS -->
<link href="css/font-awesome.css" rel="stylesheet">
<!-- jQuery -->
<!-- lined-icons -->
<link rel="stylesheet" href="css/icon-font.min.css" type='text/css' />
<!-- //lined-icons -->
<!-- chart -->
<script src="js/Chart.js"></script>
<!-- //chart -->
<!--animate-->
<link href="css/animate.css" rel="stylesheet" type="text/css" media="all">

```

```

<script src="js/wow.min.js"></script>
    <script>
        new WOW().init();
    </script>
<!--/end-animate-->
<!--webfonts-->
<link
href="//fonts.googleapis.com/css?family=Cabin:400,400italic,500,500italic,600,600italic,700,700italic'
rel='stylesheet' type='text/css'>
<!--/webfonts-->
<!-- Meters graphs -->
<script src="js/jquery-1.10.2.min.js"></script>
<!-- Placed js at the end of the document so the pages load faster -->

</head>

<body class="sign-in-up">
    <section>
        <div id="page-wrapper" class="sign-in-wrapper">
            <div class="graphs">
                <div class="sign-in-form">
                    <div class="sign-in-form-top">
                        <p><a href="index.php">Sign In</a></p>
                    </div>
                    <div class="signin">
                        <div class="signin-rit">

                            </div>

                        <form name="form1" method="post" action="">
                            <div class="log-input">

                                <div class="log-input-center">
                                    <input type="text" class="user"
Placeholder="Email Id" required="" name="email" />

```

```

        </div>

    </div>
    <div class="log-input">
        <div class="log-input-center">
            <input type="password" class="lock"
Placeholder="password" required="" name="pass"/>
        </div>

    </div>
    <input type="submit" name="btn" value="Login
to your account">

        </form>
    </div>
    <div class="new_people">
        <h4>For      New      People      <a
href="user_register.php">Register Now!</a>
        </h4>
    </div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
<!--footer section start-->

<!--footer section end-->
</section>

<script src="js/jquery.nicescroll.js"></script>
<script src="js/scripts.js"></script>
<!-- Bootstrap Core JavaScript -->
<script src="js/bootstrap.min.js"></script>
</body>
</html>
<?php
include("dbconnect.php");

```

```
session_start();
extract($_POST);

$e=$_SESSION['email'];
$xyz=mysql_query("select * from user_category where user='$e'");

if(isset($_POST['btn']))
{
$max_qry = mysql_query("select max(id) from user_category");
    $max_row = mysql_fetch_array($max_qry);
    $id=$max_row['max(id)']+1;
echo $qry=mysql_query("insert into user_category values('$id','$e','$textfield')");
if($qry)
{
?>
<script language="javascript">
alert("Success");
window.location.href="user_category.php";

</script>
<?php
}
else
{
?>
<script language="javascript">
alert("Failed");
window.location.href="user_category.php";

</script>
<?php
}

}
```

```

?>
<!DOCTYPE HTML>
<html>
<head>
<title>Easy Admin Panel an Admin Panel Category Flat Bootstrap Responsive Website Template | Short
Codes :: w3layouts</title>
<meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1">
<meta http-equiv="Content-Type" content="text/html; charset=utf-8" />
<meta name="keywords" content="Easy Admin Panel Responsive web template, Bootstrap Web
Templates, Flat Web Templates, Android Compatible web template,
Smartphone Compatible web template, free webdesigns for Nokia, Samsung, LG, SonyEricsson, Motorola
web design" />
<script type="application/x-javascript"> addEventListener("load", function() { setTimeout(hideURLbar,
0); }, false); function hideURLbar(){ window.scrollTo(0,1); } </script>
<!-- Bootstrap Core CSS -->
<link href="css/bootstrap.min.css" rel='stylesheet' type='text/css' />
<!-- Custom CSS -->
<link href="css/style.css" rel='stylesheet' type='text/css' />
<!-- Graph CSS -->
<link href="css/font-awesome.css" rel="stylesheet">
<!-- jQuery -->
<!-- lined-icons -->
<link rel="stylesheet" href="css/icon-font.min.css" type='text/css' />
<!-- //lined-icons -->
<!-- chart -->
<script src="js/Chart.js"></script>
<!-- //chart -->
<!--animate-->
<link href="css/animate.css" rel="stylesheet" type="text/css" media="all">
<script src="js/wow.min.js"></script>
    <script>
        new WOW().init();
    </script>
<!--//end-animate-->

```

```

<!--webfonts-->
<link
href='//fonts.googleapis.com/css?family=Cabin:400,400italic,500,500italic,600,600italic,700,700italic'
rel='stylesheet' type='text/css'>
<!--//webfonts-->
<!-- Meters graphs -->
<script src="js/jquery-1.10.2.min.js"></script>
<!-- Placed js at the end of the document so the pages load faster -->

</head>

<body class="sticky-header left-side-collapsed" onload="initMap()">
  <section>
    <!-- left side start-->
      <div class="left-side sticky-left-side">

        <!--logo and iconic logo start-->
        <div class="logo">
          <h1><a href="index.html">Easy <span>Admin</span></a></h1>
        </div>
        <div class="logo-icon text-center">
          <a href="index.html"><i class="lnr lnr-home"></i> </a>
        </div>

        <!--logo and iconic logo end-->
        <div class="left-side-inner">

          <!--sidebar nav start-->
          <ul class="nav nav-pills nav-stacked custom-nav">
            <li><a href="user_home.php"><i class="lnr lnr-select"></i><span>Home</span></a></li>
            <li class="active"><a href="user_category.php"><i
class="lnr lnr-cog"></i> <span>Category</span></a></li>

```

```

                <li><a href="user_income.php"><i class="lnr lnr-pencil"></i> <span>Income</span></a></li>
                <li><a href="user_expense.php"><i class="lnr lnr-indent-increase"></i> <span>Expense</span></a></li>
                <li><a href="user_view.php"><i class="lnr lnr-eye"></i> <span>View</span></a></li>
                <li><a href="user_report.php"><i class="lnr lnr-book"></i> <span>Report</span></a></li>
                <li><a href="index.php"><i class="lnr lnr-power-switch"></i> <span>Logout</span></a></li>
            </ul>
        <!--sidebar nav end-->
    </div>
</div>
<!-- left side end-->

<!-- main content start-->
<div class="main-content">
    <!-- header-starts -->
    <div class="header-section">

        <!--toggle button start-->
        <a class="toggle-btn menu-collapsed"><i class="fa fa-bars"></i></a>
        <!--toggle button end-->

        <!--notification menu start -->
        <div class="menu-right">
            <div class="user-panel-top">
                <div class="profile_details">
                    <ul>
                        <li class="dropdown profile_details_drop">
                            <a href="#" class="dropdown-toggle"
data-toggle="dropdown" aria-expanded="false">
                                <div class="profile_img">

```

```

                                <span
style="background:url(images/user1.png) no-repeat center"> </span>
                                <div      class="user-
name">
                                <p><?php echo
                                </div>
                                <i      class="lnr      lnr-
chevron-down"></i>
                                <i      class="lnr      lnr-
chevron-up"></i>
                                <div
                                class="clearfix"></div>
                                </div>
                                </a>
                                <ul class="dropdown-menu drp-mnu">
                                <li> <a href="index.php"><i
                                class="fa fa-sign-out"></i> Logout</a> </li>
                                </ul>
                                </li>
                                <div class="clearfix"> </div>
                                </ul>
                                </div>
                                </div>
                                </div>
                                <!--notification menu end -->
                                </div>
                                <!-- //header-ends -->
                                <div id="page-wrapper">
                                <div class="graphs">
                                <h3 class="blank1">Expense Category</h3>

```

```

<div class="grid_3 grid_4">
  <div class="bs-example ">
    <table class="table" >
      <tbody>
        <tr>
          <td><h1 id="h1">&nbsp;</h1></td>
          <td class="type-info"><div align="center">
            <h1>ADD NEW CATEGORY </h1>
          </div></td>
        </tr>
        <tr>
          <td class="type-info">&nbsp;</td>
          <td class="type-info"><form name="form1"
method="post" action="">
          <table width="200" border="0"
align="center">
            <tr>
              <td>Category</td>
              <td><label>
                <input type="text" name="textfield">
              </label></td>
            </tr>
            <tr>
              <td>&nbsp;</td>
              <td><label>
                <input name="btn" type="submit" id="btn" value="Submit">
                <br>
              </label></td>
            </tr>
          </table>
          </form>
          </td>
          <td class="type-info">&nbsp;</td>
        </tr>
      </tbody>
    </table>
  </div>
</div>

```

```

        <tr>
        <td>&nbsp;</td>
        <td class="type-info"><table class="table">
        <thead>
        <tr>
        <th>#</th>
        <th>Keywords</th>
        </tr>
        </thead>
        <tbody>
        <?php
            $a=1;
            while($row=mysql_fetch_array($xyz))
            {
                $b=$a%2;
                if($b==0)
                {
                    ?>
        <tr class="info">
        <?php
        }
        ?>
            <th scope="row"><?php echo $a; ?></th>
            <td><?php echo $row['category'];?></td>
        </tr>
        <?php
            $a++;
        }
        ?>
        </tbody>
        </table></td>
        <td class="type-info">&nbsp;</td>

```

```
                </tr>
            </tbody>
        </table>
    </div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
<!-- footer section start-->
    <footer>
        <p>&copy; 2019 Easy Admin Panel. All Rights Reserved | Design by
Admin.</a></p>
    </footer>
<!-- footer section end-->
</section>
```

```
<script src="js/jquery.nicescroll.js"></script>
<script src="js/scripts.js"></script>
<!-- Bootstrap Core JavaScript -->
    <script src="js/bootstrap.min.js"></script>
</body>
</html>
<?php
include("dbconnect.php");
session_start();
extract($_POST);

$e=$_SESSION['email'];
$dd =date("d");

$xyz=mysql_query("select * from user_category where user='$e'");
if(isset($_POST['btn']))
{
$max_qry = mysql_query("select max(id) from user_expense");
```

```
$max_row = mysql_fetch_array($max_qry);
$id=$max_row['max(id)']+1;
echo $qry=mysql_query("insert into user_expense values('$id','$e','$mo','$dd','$select','$amt','0')");
if($qry)
{
?>
<script language="javascript">
alert("Success");
window.location.href="user_expense.php";

</script>
<?php
}
else
{
?>
<script language="javascript">
alert("Failed");
window.location.href="user_expense.php";

</script>
<?php
}

}
?>
<!DOCTYPE HTML>
<html>
<head>
<title>Easy Admin Panel an Admin Panel Category Flat Bootstrap Responsive Website Template | Short
Codes :: w3layouts</title>
<meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1">
<meta http-equiv="Content-Type" content="text/html; charset=utf-8" />
```

```

<meta name="keywords" content="Easy Admin Panel Responsive web template, Bootstrap Web
Templates, Flat Web Templates, Android Compatible web template,
Smartphone Compatible web template, free webdesigns for Nokia, Samsung, LG, SonyEricsson, Motorola
web design" />
<script type="application/x-javascript"> addEventListener("load", function() { setTimeout(hideURLbar,
0); }, false); function hideURLbar(){ window.scrollTo(0,1); } </script>
<!-- Bootstrap Core CSS -->
<link href="css/bootstrap.min.css" rel='stylesheet' type='text/css' />
<!-- Custom CSS -->
<link href="css/style.css" rel='stylesheet' type='text/css' />
<!-- Graph CSS -->
<link href="css/font-awesome.css" rel="stylesheet">
<!-- jQuery -->
<!-- lined-icons -->
<link rel="stylesheet" href="css/icon-font.min.css" type='text/css' />
<!-- //lined-icons -->
<!-- chart -->
<script src="js/Chart.js"></script>
<!-- //chart -->
<!-- animate-->
<link href="css/animate.css" rel="stylesheet" type="text/css" media="all">
<script src="js/wow.min.js"></script>
    <script>
        new WOW().init();
    </script>
<!--//end-animate-->
<!--webfonts-->
<link
href="//fonts.googleapis.com/css?family=Cabin:400,400italic,500,500italic,600,600italic,700,700italic"
rel='stylesheet' type='text/css'>
<!--//webfonts-->
<!-- Meters graphs -->
<script src="js/jquery-1.10.2.min.js"></script>
<!-- Placed js at the end of the document so the pages load faster -->

```

```
</head>
```

```
<body class="sticky-header left-side-collapsed" onload="initMap()">
```

```
<section>
```

```
<!-- left side start-->
```

```
<div class="left-side sticky-left-side">
```

```
<!--logo and iconic logo start-->
```

```
<div class="logo">
```

```
<h1><a href="index.html">Easy <span>Admin</span></a></h1>
```

```
</div>
```

```
<div class="logo-icon text-center">
```

```
<a href="index.html"><i class="lnr lnr-home"></i> </a>
```

```
</div>
```

```
<!--logo and iconic logo end-->
```

```
<div class="left-side-inner">
```

```
<!--sidebar nav start-->
```

```
<ul class="nav nav-pills nav-stacked custom-nav">
```

```
<li><a href="user_home.php"><i class="lnr lnr-select"></i><span>Home</span></a></li>
```

```
<li><a href="user_category.php"><i class="lnr lnr-cog"></i> <span>Category</span></a></li>
```

```
<li><a href="user_income.php"><i class="lnr lnr-pencil"></i> <span>Income</span></a></li>
```

```
<li class="active"><a href="user_expense.php"><i class="lnr lnr-indent-increase"></i> <span>Expense</span></a></li>
```

```
<li><a href="user_view.php"><i class="lnr lnr-eye"></i> <span>View</span></a></li>
```

```
<li><a href="user_report.php"><i class="lnr lnr-book"></i> <span>Report</span></a></li>
```

```

                <li><a href="index.php"><i class="lnr lnr-power-
switch"></i> <span>Logout</span></a></li>
                </ul>
                <!--sidebar nav end-->
            </div>
        </div>
    <!-- left side end-->

    <!-- main content start-->
    <div class="main-content">
        <!-- header-starts -->
        <div class="header-section">

            <!--toggle button start-->
            <a class="toggle-btn menu-collapsed"><i class="fa fa-bars"></i></a>
            <!--toggle button end-->

            <!--notification menu start -->
            <div class="menu-right">
                <div class="user-panel-top">
                    <div class="profile_details">
                        <ul>
                            <li class="dropdown profile_details_drop">
                                <a href="#" class="dropdown-toggle"
data-toggle="dropdown" aria-expanded="false">
                                    <div class="profile_img">
                                        <span
style="background:url(images/user1.png) no-repeat center"> </span>
                                        <div class="user-
name">
                                            <p><?php echo
$e;?><span>user</span></p>
                                        </div>

```

```

chevron-down"></i>
chevron-up"></i>
class="clearfix"></div>

<i class="lnr lnr-
<i class="lnr lnr-
<div
</div>
</a>
<ul class="dropdown-menu drp-mnu">
<li> <a href="index.php"><i
class="fa fa-sign-out"></i> Logout</a> </li>
</ul>
</li>
<div class="clearfix"> </div>
</ul>
</div>
</div>
</div>
<!--notification menu end -->
</div>
<!-- //header-ends -->
<div id="page-wrapper">
<div class="graphs">
<h3 class="blank1">USER EXPENSE DETAILS </h3>
<div class="grid_3 grid_4">
<div class="bs-example ">
<table class="table" >
<tbody>
<tr>
<td><h1 id="h1">&nbsp;</h1></td>
<td class="type-info"><div align="center">

```

```

        <h1>ADD EXPENSE </h1>
    </div></td>
    <td class="type-info">&nbsp;</td>
</tr>
<tr>
<td>&nbsp;</td>
<td class="type-info"><form name="form1"
method="post" action="">
<table width="200" border="0"
align="center">
    <tr>
        <td>Month</td>
        <td><label>
            <input name="mo" type="text" id="mo" value="<?php echo $date =date("m"); ?>"
        >
        </label></td>
    </tr>
    <tr>
        <td>Category</td>
        <td><label>
            <select name="select">
                <?php
while($row=mysql_fetch_array($xyz))
            {
                <?php
                <option value="<?php echo $row['category'];?>"><?php echo
                $row['category'];?></option>
                <?php
            }
        <?php
            </select>

```

```

        </label></td>
    </tr>
    <tr>
        <td>Amount</td>
        <td><label>
            <input type="number" name="amt" required="" placeholder="Amount">
        </label></td>
    </tr>
    <tr>
        <td>&nbsp;</td>
        <td><label>
            <input name="btn" type="submit" id="btn" value="Submit">
            <br>
        </label></td>
    </tr>
</table>
                </form>
            </td>
            <td class="type-info">&nbsp;</td>
        </tr>
    </tbody>
</table>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
<!--footer section start-->
    <footer>
        <p>&copy; 2019 Easy Admin Panel. All Rights Reserved | Design by
Admin.</a></p>
    </footer>
<!--footer section end-->
</section>

```

```

<script src="js/jquery.nicescroll.js"></script>
<script src="js/scripts.js"></script>
<!-- Bootstrap Core JavaScript -->
  <script src="js/bootstrap.min.js"></script>
</body>
</html>
<?php
include("dbconnect.php");
session_start();
extract($_POST);

$e=$_SESSION['email'];
$xyz=mysql_query("select * from user_expense where user='$e'");

$total=0;
$income=0;
$xyz1=mysql_query("select * from user_income where user='$e'");
while($row1=mysql_fetch_array($xyz1))
    {
        $income=$income+$row1['amount'];
    }
while($row=mysql_fetch_array($xyz))
    {
        $total= $total+$row['amount'];
    }
?>
<!DOCTYPE HTML>
<html>
<head>
<title>Easy Admin Panel an Admin Panel Category Flat Bootstrap Responsive Website Template | Home
:: w3layouts</title>
<meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1">
<meta http-equiv="Content-Type" content="text/html; charset=utf-8" />

```

```

<meta name="keywords" content="Easy Admin Panel Responsive web template, Bootstrap Web
Templates, Flat Web Templates, Android Compatible web template,
Smartphone Compatible web template, free webdesigns for Nokia, Samsung, LG, SonyEricsson, Motorola
web design" />
<script type="application/x-javascript"> addEventListener("load", function() { setTimeout(hideURLbar,
0); }, false); function hideURLbar(){ window.scrollTo(0,1); } </script>
<!-- Bootstrap Core CSS -->
<link href="css/bootstrap.min.css" rel='stylesheet' type='text/css' />
<!-- Custom CSS -->
<link href="css/style.css" rel='stylesheet' type='text/css' />
<!-- Graph CSS -->
<link href="css/font-awesome.css" rel="stylesheet">
<!-- jQuery -->
<!-- lined-icons -->
<link rel="stylesheet" href="css/icon-font.min.css" type='text/css' />
<!-- //lined-icons -->
<!-- chart -->
<script src="js/Chart.js"></script>
<!-- //chart -->
<!-- animate-->
<link href="css/animate.css" rel="stylesheet" type="text/css" media="all">
<script src="js/wow.min.js"></script>
    <script>
        new WOW().init();
    </script>
<!--//end-animate-->
<!--webfonts-->
<link
href="//fonts.googleapis.com/css?family=Cabin:400,400italic,500,500italic,600,600italic,700,700italic"
rel='stylesheet' type='text/css'>
<!--//webfonts-->
<!-- Meters graphs -->
<script src="js/jquery-1.10.2.min.js"></script>
<!-- Placed js at the end of the document so the pages load faster -->

```

```

</head>

<body class="sticky-header left-side-collapsed" onload="initMap()">
  <section>
    <!-- left side start-->
      <div class="left-side sticky-left-side">

        <!--logo and iconic logo start-->
        <div class="logo">
          <h1><a href="user_home.php">Expense
<span>Tracker</span></a></h1>
        </div>
        <div class="logo-icon text-center">
          <a href="user_home.php"><i class="lnr lnr-home"></i> </a>
        </div>

        <!--logo and iconic logo end-->
        <div class="left-side-inner">

          <!--sidebar nav start-->
          <ul class="nav nav-pills nav-stacked custom-nav">
            <li class="active"><a href="user_home.php"><i
class="lnr lnr-select"></i><span>Home</span></a></li>
            <li><a href="user_category.php"><i class="lnr lnr-
cog"></i> <span>Category</span></a></li>
            <li><a href="user_income.php"><i class="lnr lnr-
pencil"></i> <span>Income</span></a></li>
            <li><a href="user_expense.php"><i class="lnr lnr-
indent-increase"></i> <span>Expense</span></a></li>
            <li><a href="user_view.php"><i class="lnr lnr-
eye"></i> <span>View</span></a></li>
            <li><a href="user_report.php"><i class="lnr lnr-
book"></i> <span>Report</span></a></li>

```

```
switch"></i> <span>Logout</span></a></li>
```

```
</ul>
```

```
<!--sidebar nav end-->
```

```
</div>
```

```
</div>
```

```
<!-- left side end-->
```

```
<!-- main content start-->
```

```
<div class="main-content">
```

```
<!-- header-starts -->
```

```
<div class="header-section">
```

```
<!--toggle button start-->
```

```
<a class="toggle-btn menu-collapsed"><i class="fa fa-bars"></i></a>
```

```
<!--toggle button end-->
```

```
<!--notification menu start -->
```

```
<div class="menu-right">
```

```
<div class="user-panel-top">
```

```
<div class="profile_details_left">
```

```
</div>
```

```
<div class="profile_details">
```

```
<ul>
```

```
<li class="dropdown profile_details_drop">
```

```
<a href="#" class="dropdown-toggle"
```

```
data-toggle="dropdown" aria-expanded="false">
```

```
<div class="profile_img">
```

```
<span
```

```
style="background:url(images/user1.png) no-repeat center"> </span>
```

```

name">
                                <div class="user-
                                <p><?php echo
                                </p>
                                </div>
                                <i class="lnr lnr-
                                <i class="lnr lnr-
                                <div
                                class="clearfix"></div>
                                </div>
                                </a>
                                <ul class="dropdown-menu drp-mnu">
                                <li> <a href="index.php"><i
                                class="fa fa-sign-out"></i> Logout</a> </li>
                                </ul>
                                </li>
                                <div class="clearfix"> </div>
                                </ul>
                                </div>
                                <div class="clearfix"></div>
                                </div>
                                </div>
                                <!--notification menu end -->
                                </div>
                                <!-- //header-ends -->
                                <div id="page-wrapper">
                                <div class="graphs">
                                <div class="col_3">

```

```

<div class="col-md-3 widget widget1">
  <div class="r3_counter_box"> <i class="fa fa-mail-forward"></i>
    <div class="stats">
      <h5>
        <?php
          echo $income;
        ?>
      </h5>
      <span>${</span></h5>
    </div>
    <div class="grow">
      <p>Amount</p>
    </div>
  </div>
</div>
<div class="col-md-3 widget widget1">
  <div class="r3_counter_box"> <i class="fa fa-users"></i>
    <div class="stats">
      <h5> 100 <span>%</span></h5>
      <div class="grow grow1">
        <p>Income</p>
      </div>
    </div>
  </div>
</div>
<div class="col-md-3 widget widget1">
  <div class="r3_counter_box"> <i class="fa fa-eye"></i>
    <div class="stats">
      <h5>
        <?php
          $exp=($total/$income)*100;
        ?>
      </h5>
    </div>
  </div>
</div>

```

```

        echo round($exp);

    ?>

    <span>%</span></h5>
    <div class="grow grow3">
        <p>Expense</p>
    </div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
<div class="col-md-3 widget">
    <div class="r3_counter_box"> <i class="fa fa-usd"></i>
        <div class="stats">
            <h5>
                <?php

                    $profit=100-$exp;
                    echo round($profit);

                ?>

            <span>%</span></h5>
            <div class="grow grow2">
                <p>Profit</p>
            </div>
        </div>
    </div>
</div>
<div class="clearfix"> </div>
</div>

        <!-- switches -->
        <!-- //switches -->
</div>

        <!--body wrapper start-->
</div>

```

```

                <!--body wrapper end-->
            </div>
        <!--footer section start-->
            <footer>
                <p>&copy 2019 Easy Admin Panel. All Rights Reserved | Design by admin.</p>
            </footer>
        <!--footer section end-->

        <!-- main content end-->
    </section>

    <script src="js/jquery.nicescroll.js"></script>
    <script src="js/scripts.js"></script>
    <!-- Bootstrap Core JavaScript -->
    <script src="js/bootstrap.min.js"></script>
</body>
</html>
<?php
include("dbconnect.php");
session_start();
extract($_POST);

$e=$_SESSION['email'];

if(isset($_POST['btn']))
{
$max_qry = mysql_query("select max(id) from user_income");
    $max_row = mysql_fetch_array($max_qry);
    $id=$max_row['max(id)']+1;
echo $qry=mysql_query("insert into user_income values('$id','$e','$amt','$select')");
if($qry)
{
?>

```

```
<script language="javascript">
alert("Success");
window.location.href="user_income.php";

</script>
<?php
}
else
{
?>
<script language="javascript">
alert("Failed");
window.location.href="user_income.php";

</script>
<?php
}

}
?>
<!DOCTYPE HTML>
<html>
<head>
<title>Easy Admin Panel an Admin Panel Category Flat Bootstrap Responsive Website Template | Short
Codes :: w3layouts</title>
<meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1">
<meta http-equiv="Content-Type" content="text/html; charset=utf-8" />
<meta name="keywords" content="Easy Admin Panel Responsive web template, Bootstrap Web
Templates, Flat Web Templates, Android Compatible web template,
Smartphone Compatible web template, free webdesigns for Nokia, Samsung, LG, SonyEricsson, Motorola
web design" />
<script type="application/x-javascript"> addEventListener("load", function() { setTimeout(hideURLbar,
0); }, false); function hideURLbar(){ window.scrollTo(0,1); } </script>
<!-- Bootstrap Core CSS -->
```

```

<link href="css/bootstrap.min.css" rel='stylesheet' type='text/css' />
<!-- Custom CSS -->
<link href="css/style.css" rel='stylesheet' type='text/css' />
<!-- Graph CSS -->
<link href="css/font-awesome.css" rel="stylesheet">
<!-- jQuery -->
<!-- lined-icons -->
<link rel="stylesheet" href="css/icon-font.min.css" type='text/css' />
<!-- //lined-icons -->
<!-- chart -->
<script src="js/Chart.js"></script>
<!-- //chart -->
<!--animate-->
<link href="css/animate.css" rel="stylesheet" type="text/css" media="all">
<script src="js/wow.min.js"></script>
    <script>
        new WOW().init();
    </script>
<!--//end-animate-->
<!--webfonts-->
<link
href="//fonts.googleapis.com/css?family=Cabin:400,400italic,500,500italic,600,600italic,700,700italic'
rel='stylesheet' type='text/css'>
<!--//webfonts-->
<!-- Meters graphs -->
<script src="js/jquery-1.10.2.min.js"></script>
<!-- Placed js at the end of the document so the pages load faster -->

</head>

<body class="sticky-header left-side-collapsed" onload="initMap()">
    <section>
        <!-- left side start-->
            <div class="left-side sticky-left-side">

```

```

<!--logo and iconic logo start-->
<div class="logo">
    <h1><a href="index.html">Easy <span>Admin</span></a></h1>
</div>
<div class="logo-icon text-center">
    <a href="index.html"><i class="lnr lnr-home"></i> </a>
</div>

<!--logo and iconic logo end-->
<div class="left-side-inner">

    <!--sidebar nav start-->
        <ul class="nav nav-pills nav-stacked custom-nav">
            <li><a href="user_home.php"><i class="lnr lnr-
select"></i><span>Home</span></a></li>
            <li ><a href="user_category.php"><i class="lnr lnr-
cog"></i> <span>Category</span></a></li>
            <li class="active"><a href="user_income.php"><i
class="lnr lnr-pencil"></i> <span>Income</span></a></li>
            <li><a href="user_expense.php"><i class="lnr lnr-
indent-increase"></i> <span>Expense</span></a></li>
            <li><a href="user_view.php"><i class="lnr lnr-
eye"></i> <span>View</span></a></li>
            <li><a href="user_report.php"><i class="lnr lnr-
book"></i> <span>Report</span></a></li>
            <li><a href="index.php"><i class="lnr lnr-power-
switch"></i> <span>Logout</span></a></li>
        </ul>
    <!--sidebar nav end-->
</div>
</div>
<!-- left side end-->

```

```

<!-- main content start-->
    <div class="main-content">
        <!-- header-starts -->
        <div class="header-section">

            <!--toggle button start-->
            <a class="toggle-btn menu-collapsed"><i class="fa fa-bars"></i></a>
            <!--toggle button end-->

            <!--notification menu start -->
            <div class="menu-right">
                <div class="user-panel-top">
                    <div class="profile_details">
                        <ul>
                            <li class="dropdown profile_details_drop">
                                <a href="#" class="dropdown-toggle"
data-toggle="dropdown" aria-expanded="false">
                                    <div class="profile_img">
                                        <span
style="background:url(images/user1.png) no-repeat center"> </span>
                                        <div class="user-
name">
                                            <p><?php echo
$e;?><span>user</span></p>
                                        </div>
                                        <i class="lnr lnr-
chevron-down"></i>
                                        <i class="lnr lnr-
chevron-up"></i>
                                        <div
class="clearfix"></div>
                                    </div>
                                </a>
                                <ul class="dropdown-menu drp-mnu">

```

```

class="fa fa-sign-out"></i> Logout</a> </li>
</li>
</ul>
</div>
</div>
<!--notification menu end -->
</div>
<!-- //header-ends -->
<div id="page-wrapper">
<div class="graphs">
<h3 class="blank1">USER INCOME DETAILS </h3>
<div class="grid_3 grid_4">
<div class="bs-example ">
<table class="table" >
<tbody>
<tr>
<td><h1 id="h1">&nbsp;</h1></td>
<td class="type-info"><div align="center">
<h1>ADD INCOME </h1>
</div></td>
<td class="type-info">&nbsp;</td>
</tr>
<tr>
<td>&nbsp;</td>
<td class="type-info"><form name="form1"
method="post" action="">

```

```

align="center">
        <table        width="200"        border="0"
        <tr>
        <td>Amount</td>
        <td><label>
        <input type="number" name="amt" required="" placeholder="Amount">
        </label></td>
        </tr>
        <tr>
        <td>Month</td>
        <td><label>
        <select name="select">
                <?php
                $i=1;
                for($i;$i<=12;$i++)
                {
                ?>
                <option value="<?php echo $i;?>"><?php echo $i;?></option>
                <?php
                }
                ?>
        </select>
        </label></td>
        </tr>
        <tr>
        <td>&nbsp;</td>
        <td><label>
        <input name="btn" type="submit" id="btn" value="Submit">
        <br>
        </label></td>
        </tr>
</table>
        </form>
        </td>
        <td class="type-info">&nbsp;</td>

```

```

                </tr>
            </tbody>
        </table>
    </div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
<!-- footer section start-->
    <footer>
        <p>&copy; 2019 Easy Admin Panel. All Rights Reserved | Design by
Admin.</a></p>
    </footer>
<!-- footer section end-->
</section>

<script src="js/jquery.nicescroll.js"></script>
<script src="js/scripts.js"></script>
<!-- Bootstrap Core JavaScript -->
    <script src="js/bootstrap.min.js"></script>
</body>
</html>
<?php
include("dbconnect.php");
session_start();
extract($_POST);
if(isset($_POST['Submit2']))
{
    $date =date("d-m-y");
    $max_qry = mysql_query("select max(id) from user_details");
        $max_row = mysql_fetch_array($max_qry);
        $id=$max_row['max(id)']+1;
echo          $qry=mysql_query("insert          into          user_details
values('$id','$username','$contact','$email','$address','$pass','$date)");

```

```
if($qry)
{
?>
<script language="javascript">
alert("Register Successfully..");
window.location.href="index.php";
</script>
<?php
}
else
{
?>
<script language="javascript">
alert("Failed..");
window.location.href="user_register.php";
</script>
<?php
}
}

?>
<!DOCTYPE HTML>
<html>
<head>
<title>Easy Admin Panel an Admin Panel Category Flat Bootstrap Responsive Website Template | Sign In
:: w3layouts</title>
<meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1">
<meta http-equiv="Content-Type" content="text/html; charset=utf-8" />
<meta name="keywords" content="Easy Admin Panel Responsive web template, Bootstrap Web
Templates, Flat Web Templates, Android Compatible web template,
Smartphone Compatible web template, free webdesigns for Nokia, Samsung, LG, SonyEricsson, Motorola
web design" />
```

```

<script type="application/x-javascript"> addEventListener("load", function() { setTimeout(hideURLbar,
0); }, false); function hideURLbar(){ window.scrollTo(0,1); } </script>
<!-- Bootstrap Core CSS -->
<link href="css/bootstrap.min.css" rel='stylesheet' type='text/css' />
<!-- Custom CSS -->
<link href="css/style.css" rel='stylesheet' type='text/css' />
<!-- Graph CSS -->
<link href="css/font-awesome.css" rel="stylesheet">
<!-- jQuery -->
<!-- lined-icons -->
<link rel="stylesheet" href="css/icon-font.min.css" type='text/css' />
<!-- //lined-icons -->
<!-- chart -->
<script src="js/Chart.js"></script>
<!-- //chart -->
<!--animate-->
<link href="css/animate.css" rel="stylesheet" type="text/css" media="all">
<script src="js/wow.min.js"></script>
    <script>
        new WOW().init();
    </script>
<!--//end-animate-->
<!--webfonts-->
<link
href="//fonts.googleapis.com/css?family=Cabin:400,400italic,500,500italic,600,600italic,700,700italic"
rel='stylesheet' type='text/css'>
<!--//webfonts-->
<!-- Meters graphs -->
<script src="js/jquery-1.10.2.min.js"></script>
<!-- Placed js at the end of the document so the pages load faster -->

</head>

<body class="sign-in-up">

```

<section>

<div id="page-wrapper" class="sign-in-wrapper">

<div class="graphs">

<div class="sign-in-form">

<div class="sign-in-form-top">

<p>Sign Up </p>

</div>

<div class="signin">

<form name="form1" method="post" action="">

<div class="log-input">

<div class="log-input-center">

<input type="text"

Placeholder="Your Name" required="" name="username" />

</div>

</div>

<div class="log-input">

<div class="log-input-center">

<input type="text"

Placeholder="Contact" required="" name="contact" />

</div>

</div>

<div class="log-input">

<div class="log-input-center">

<input type="text"

Placeholder="Email" required="" name="email" />

</div>

</div>

```

        <div class="log-input">
            <div class="log-input-center">
                <input
Placeholder="Address" required="" name="address" />
                    type="text"
                </div>
            </div>
        </div>
        <div class="log-input">
            <div class="log-input-center">
                <input
Placeholder="password" required="" name="pass"/>
                    type="password"
                </div>
            </div>
            <input
value="Register your account Now">
                type="submit"
                name="Submit2"
            </form>
        </div>
    </div>
</div>
<!--footer section start-->
<!--footer section end-->
</section>
<script src="js/jquery.nicescroll.js"></script>
<script src="js/scripts.js"></script>

```

```

<!-- Bootstrap Core JavaScript -->
  <script src="js/bootstrap.min.js"></script>
</body>
</html>
<?php
include("dbconnect.php");
session_start();
extract($_POST);

$e=$_SESSION['email'];
if(isset($_POST['btn']))
{
$_SESSION['dd']=$select;
header("Location:user_report_1.php?dd=$select");
}
?>
<!DOCTYPE HTML>
<html>
<head>
<title>Easy Admin Panel an Admin Panel Category Flat Bootstrap Responsive Website Template | Short
Codes :: w3layouts</title>
<meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1">
<meta http-equiv="Content-Type" content="text/html; charset=utf-8" />
<meta name="keywords" content="Easy Admin Panel Responsive web template, Bootstrap Web
Templates, Flat Web Templates, Android Compatible web template,
Smartphone Compatible web template, free webdesigns for Nokia, Samsung, LG, SonyEricsson, Motorola
web design" />
<script type="application/x-javascript"> addEventListener("load", function() { setTimeout(hideURLbar,
0); }, false); function hideURLbar(){ window.scrollTo(0,1); } </script>
<!-- Bootstrap Core CSS -->
<link href="css/bootstrap.min.css" rel='stylesheet' type='text/css' />
<!-- Custom CSS -->
<link href="css/style.css" rel='stylesheet' type='text/css' />
<!-- Graph CSS -->

```

```

<link href="css/font-awesome.css" rel="stylesheet">
<!-- jQuery -->
<!-- lined-icons -->
<link rel="stylesheet" href="css/icon-font.min.css" type='text/css' />
<!-- //lined-icons -->
<!-- chart -->
<script src="js/Chart.js"></script>
<!-- //chart -->
<!-- animate-->
<link href="css/animate.css" rel="stylesheet" type="text/css" media="all">
<script src="js/wow.min.js"></script>
    <script>
        new WOW().init();
    </script>
<!--//end-animate-->
<!---webfonts-->
<link
href="//fonts.googleapis.com/css?family=Cabin:400,400italic,500,500italic,600,600italic,700,700italic"
rel='stylesheet' type='text/css'>
<!---//webfonts-->
<!-- Meters graphs -->
<script src="js/jquery-1.10.2.min.js"></script>
<!-- Placed js at the end of the document so the pages load faster -->

</head>

<body class="sticky-header left-side-collapsed" onload="initMap()">
    <section>
        <!-- left side start-->
            <div class="left-side sticky-left-side">

                <!--logo and iconic logo start-->
                <div class="logo">
                    <h1><a href="index.html">Easy <span>Admin</span></a></h1>

```

```

        </div>
        <div class="logo-icon text-center">
            <a href="index.html"><i class="lnr lnr-home"></i> </a>
        </div>

        <!-- logo and iconic logo end-->
        <div class="left-side-inner">

            <!-- sidebar nav start-->
            <ul class="nav nav-pills nav-stacked custom-nav">
                <li><a href="user_home.php"><i class="lnr lnr-
select"></i><span>Home</span></a></li>
                <li><a href="user_category.php"><i class="lnr lnr-
cog"></i> <span>Category</span></a></li>
                <li><a href="user_income.php"><i class="lnr lnr-
pencil"></i> <span>Income</span></a></li>
                <li><a href="user_expense.php"><i class="lnr lnr-
indent-increase"></i> <span>Expense</span></a></li>
                <li><a href="user_view.php"><i class="lnr lnr-
eye"></i> <span>View</span></a></li>
                <li class="active"><a href="user_report.php"><i
class="lnr lnr-book"></i> <span>Report</span></a></li>
                <li><a href="index.php"><i class="lnr lnr-power-
switch"></i> <span>Logout</span></a></li>
            </ul>
            <!-- sidebar nav end-->
        </div>
    </div>
<!-- left side end-->

<!-- main content start-->
    <div class="main-content">
        <!-- header-starts -->
        <div class="header-section">

```

```

        <!--toggle button start-->
        <a class="toggle-btn menu-collapsed"><i class="fa fa-bars"></i></a>
        <!--toggle button end-->

        <!--notification menu start -->
        <div class="menu-right">
            <div class="user-panel-top">
                <div class="profile_details">
                    <ul>
                        <li class="dropdown profile_details_drop">
                            <a href="#" class="dropdown-toggle"
data-toggle="dropdown" aria-expanded="false">
                                <div class="profile_img">
                                    <span
style="background:url(images/user1.png) no-repeat center"> </span>
                                    <div class="user-
name">
                                        <p><?php echo
$e;?><span>user</span></p>
                                        </div>
                                        <i class="lnr lnr-
chevron-down"></i>
                                        <i class="lnr lnr-
chevron-up"></i>
                                    <div
class="clearfix"></div>
                                </div>
                            </a>
                            <ul class="dropdown-menu drp-mnu">
                                <li> <a href="index.php"><i
class="fa fa-sign-out"></i> Logout</a> </li>
                                </ul>
                    </li>
                </ul>
            </div>
        </div>
    </div>

```

```

                </li>
                <div class="clearfix"> </div>
            </ul>
        </div>

        </div>
    </div>
    <!--notification menu end -->
    </div>
<!-- //header-ends -->
    <div id="page-wrapper">
        <div class="graphs">
            <h3 class="blank1">Expense Details </h3>
            <div class="grid_3 grid_4">
                <div class="bs-example ">
                    <table class="table" >
                        <tbody>
                            <tr>
                                <td><h1 id="h1">&nbsp;</h1></td>
                                <td class="type-info"><div align="center">
                                    <h1>EXPENSE REPORT </h1>
                                </div></td>
                                <td class="type-info">&nbsp;</td>
                            </tr>
                            <tr>
                                <td>&nbsp;</td>
                                <td class="type-info"><form name="form1"
method="post" action="">
                                <table width="200" border="0"
align="center">
                                    <tr>
                                        <td>Month</td>
                                        <td><select name="select">

```

```

        <?php
            $i=1;
            for($i;$i<=12;$i++)
            {
                ?>
                <option value="<?php echo $i;?>"><?php echo $i;?></option>
            <?php
                }
            ?>
        </select></td>
    </tr>
    <tr>
        <td>&nbsp;</td>
        <td><label></label>
        <label>
            <input name="btn" type="submit" id="btn" value="Submit">
        </label></td>
    </tr>
</table>
</form>
</td>
<td class="type-info">&nbsp;</td>
</tr>
</tbody>
</table>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
<!-- footer section start-->
<footer>
    <p>&copy; 2019 Easy Admin Panel. All Rights Reserved | Design by
Admin.</a></p>

```

```

        </footer>
    <!--footer section end-->
    </section>

<script src="js/jquery.nicescroll.js"></script>
<script src="js/scripts.js"></script>
<!-- Bootstrap Core JavaScript -->
    <script src="js/bootstrap.min.js"></script>
</body>
</html>
<?php
include("dbconnect.php");
session_start();
extract($_POST);
$dd=$_SESSION['dd'];
$e=$_SESSION['email'];
$xyz=mysql_query("select * from user_expense where user='$e' and month='$dd'");

$total=0;
$xyz1=mysql_query("select * from user_income where user='$e' and month='$dd'");
while($row1=mysql_fetch_array($xyz1))
    {
        $income=$row1['amount'];
    }

?>
<!DOCTYPE HTML>
<html>
<head>
<title>Easy Admin Panel an Admin Panel Category Flat Bootstrap Responsive Website Template | Short
Codes :: w3layouts</title>
<meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1">
<meta http-equiv="Content-Type" content="text/html; charset=utf-8" />
<meta name="keywords" content="Easy Admin Panel Responsive web template, Bootstrap Web
Templates, Flat Web Templates, Android Compatible web template,

```

Smartphone Compatible web template, free webdesigns for Nokia, Samsung, LG, SonyEricsson, Motorola web design" />

```
<script type="application/x-javascript"> addEventListener("load", function() { setTimeout(hideURLbar, 0); }, false); function hideURLbar(){ window.scrollTo(0,1); } </script>
```

```
<!-- Bootstrap Core CSS -->
```

```
<link href="css/bootstrap.min.css" rel='stylesheet' type='text/css' />
```

```
<!-- Custom CSS -->
```

```
<link href="css/style.css" rel='stylesheet' type='text/css' />
```

```
<!-- Graph CSS -->
```

```
<link href="css/font-awesome.css" rel="stylesheet">
```

```
<!-- jQuery -->
```

```
<!-- lined-icons -->
```

```
<link rel="stylesheet" href="css/icon-font.min.css" type='text/css' />
```

```
<!-- //lined-icons -->
```

```
<!-- chart -->
```

```
<script src="js/Chart.js"></script>
```

```
<!-- //chart -->
```

```
<!--animate-->
```

```
<link href="css/animate.css" rel="stylesheet" type="text/css" media="all">
```

```
<script src="js/wow.min.js"></script>
```

```
<script>
```

```
new WOW().init();
```

```
</script>
```

```
<!--//end-animate-->
```

```
<!--webfonts-->
```

```
<link
```

```
href="//fonts.googleapis.com/css?family=Cabin:400,400italic,500,500italic,600,600italic,700,700italic'
```

```
rel='stylesheet' type='text/css'>
```

```
<!--//webfonts-->
```

```
<!-- Meters graphs -->
```

```
<script src="js/jquery-1.10.2.min.js"></script>
```

```
<!-- Placed js at the end of the document so the pages load faster -->
```

```
</head>
```

```

<body class="sticky-header left-side-collapsed" onload="initMap()">
  <section>
  <!-- left side start-->
    <div class="left-side sticky-left-side">

      <!--logo and iconic logo start-->
      <div class="logo">
        <h1><a href="index.php">Easy <span>Admin</span></a></h1>
      </div>
      <div class="logo-icon text-center">
        <a href="index.php"><i class="lnr lnr-home"></i> </a>
      </div>

      <!--logo and iconic logo end-->
      <div class="left-side-inner">

        <!--sidebar nav start-->
        <ul class="nav nav-pills nav-stacked custom-nav">
          <li><a href="user_home.php"><i class="lnr lnr-select"></i><span>Home</span></a></li>
          <li>><a href="user_category.php"><i class="lnr lnr-cog"></i> <span>Category</span></a></li>
          <li><a href="user_income.php"><i class="lnr lnr-pencil"></i> <span>Income</span></a></li>
          <li><a href="user_expense.php"><i class="lnr lnr-indent-increase"></i> <span>Expense</span></a></li>
          <li>><a href="user_view.php"><i class="lnr lnr-eye"></i> <span>View</span></a></li>
          <li class="active"><a href="user_report.php"><i class="lnr lnr-book"></i> <span>Report</span></a></li>
          <li><a href="index.php"><i class="lnr lnr-power-switch"></i> <span>Logout</span></a></li>
        </ul>

```

```

                <!--sidebar nav end-->
            </div>
        </div>
<!-- left side end-->

<!-- main content start-->
    <div class="main-content">
        <!-- header-starts -->
        <div class="header-section">

            <!--toggle button start-->
            <a class="toggle-btn menu-collapsed"><i class="fa fa-bars"></i></a>
            <!--toggle button end-->

            <!--notification menu start -->
            <div class="menu-right">
                <div class="user-panel-top">
                    <div class="profile_details">
                        <ul>
                            <li class="dropdown profile_details_drop">
                                <a href="#" class="dropdown-toggle"
data-toggle="dropdown" aria-expanded="false">
                                    <div class="profile_img">
                                        <span
style="background:url(images/user1.png) no-repeat center"> </span>
                                        <div class="user-
name">
                                            <p><?php echo
$e;?><span>user</span></p>
                                        </div>
                                        <i class="lnr lnr-
chevron-down"></i>
                                        <i class="lnr lnr-
chevron-up"></i>

```



```

        <td>&nbsp;</td>
        <td class="type-info"><table class="table">
</thead>
<tr>
<th>#</th>
<th>Date</th>
<th>Month</th>
<th>Category</th>
<th>Amount</th>
</tr>
</thead>
<tbody>
<?php
        $a=1;
        while($row=mysql_fetch_array($xyz))
        {
            $b=$a%2;
            if($b==0)
            {
                ?>
<tr class="info">
<?php
    }
?>

<th scope="row"><?php echo $a; ?></th>
<td><?php echo $row['cdate'];?></td>
<td><?php echo $row['month'];?></td>
<td><?php echo $row['category'];?></td>
<td><?php echo $row['amount'];
        $total= $total+$row['amount'];
        ?></td>

```

```

</tr>

<?php
    $a++;
    }
?>

<tr >
    <th scope="row">&nbsp;</th>
    <td>&nbsp;</td>
    <td>&nbsp;</td>
    <td>&nbsp;</td>
    <td>&nbsp;</td>
</tr>
<tr class="danger">
<th scope="row">&nbsp;</th>
<td>&nbsp;</td>
<td>&nbsp;</td>
<td>Total Expense </td>
<td><?php echo $total;?>&nbsp;</td>
</tr>

<tr class="danger">
    <th scope="row">&nbsp;</th>
    <td>&nbsp;</td>
    <td>&nbsp;</td>
    <td>Total Income </td>
    <td><?php echo $income;?>&nbsp;</td>
</tr>

<tr class="danger">
    <th scope="row">&nbsp;</th>
    <td>&nbsp;</td>
    <td>&nbsp;</td>
    <td>Balance</td>
    <td><?php
        $a=$income-$total;

```

```

        echo $a;

        ?&nbsp;</td>

    </tr>

</tbody>
</table></td>

        <td class="type-info">&nbsp;</td>

    </tr>

</tbody>
</table>

</div>

</div>

</div>

    <div class="graphs">
<div class="col_3">
    <div class="col-md-3 widget widget1">
        <div class="r3_counter_box"> <i class="fa fa-mail-forward"></i>
        <div class="stats">
            <h5>
                <?php

                    echo $income;

                ?>

            <span>${</span></h5>
        <div class="grow">
            <p>Amount</p>
        </div>
    </div>
</div>

</div>

<div class="col-md-3 widget widget1">
    <div class="r3_counter_box"> <i class="fa fa-users"></i>

```

```

    <div class="stats">
      <h5> 100 <span>%</span></h5>
      <div class="grow grow1">
        <p>Income</p>
      </div>
    </div>
  </div>
</div>
<div class="col-md-3 widget widget1">
  <div class="r3_counter_box"> <i class="fa fa-eye"></i>
    <div class="stats">
      <h5>
        <?php
                                echo $exp=(($total/$income)*100;
                                ?>
        <span>%</span></h5>
      <div class="grow grow3">
        <p>Expense</p>
      </div>
    </div>
  </div>
</div>
<div class="col-md-3 widget">
  <div class="r3_counter_box"> <i class="fa fa-usd"></i>
    <div class="stats">
      <h5>
        <?php
                                echo $profit=100-$exp;

```

?>

```
<span>%</span></h5>
<div class="grow grow2">
  <p>Profit</p>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
<div class="clearfix"> </div>
</div>
      <!-- switches -->
<div class="switches">
  <div class="col-4"></div>
</div>
      <!-- //switches -->
</div>
      </div>
</div>
<!--footer section start-->
  <footer>
    <p>&copy; 2019 Easy Admin Panel. All Rights Reserved | Design by
Admin.</a></p>
  </footer>
<!--footer section end-->
</section>

<script src="js/jquery.nicescroll.js"></script>
<script src="js/scripts.js"></script>
<!-- Bootstrap Core JavaScript -->
  <script src="js/bootstrap.min.js"></script>
</body>
</html>
<?php
include("dbconnect.php");
```

```

session_start();
extract($_POST);
$dd =date("m");
$e=$_SESSION['email'];
$xyz=mysql_query("select * from user_expense where user='$e' and month='$dd'");

$total=0;
$xyz1=mysql_query("select * from user_income where user='$e' and month='$dd'");
while($row1=mysql_fetch_array($xyz1))
    {
        $income=$row1['amount'];
    }

?>
<!DOCTYPE HTML>
<html>
<head>
<title>Easy Admin Panel an Admin Panel Category Flat Bootstrap Responsive Website Template | Short
Codes :: w3layouts</title>
<meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1">
<meta http-equiv="Content-Type" content="text/html; charset=utf-8" />
<meta name="keywords" content="Easy Admin Panel Responsive web template, Bootstrap Web
Templates, Flat Web Templates, Android Compatible web template,
Smartphone Compatible web template, free webdesigns for Nokia, Samsung, LG, SonyEricsson, Motorola
web design" />
<script type="application/x-javascript"> addEventListener("load", function() { setTimeout(hideURLbar,
0); }, false); function hideURLbar(){ window.scrollTo(0,1); } </script>
<!-- Bootstrap Core CSS -->
<link href="css/bootstrap.min.css" rel='stylesheet' type='text/css' />
<!-- Custom CSS -->
<link href="css/style.css" rel='stylesheet' type='text/css' />
<!-- Graph CSS -->
<link href="css/font-awesome.css" rel="stylesheet">
<!-- jQuery -->
<!-- lined-icons -->

```

```

<link rel="stylesheet" href="css/icon-font.min.css" type='text/css' />
<!-- //lined-icons -->
<!-- chart -->
<script src="js/Chart.js"></script>
<!-- //chart -->
<!--animate-->
<link href="css/animate.css" rel="stylesheet" type="text/css" media="all">
<script src="js/wow.min.js"></script>
    <script>
        new WOW().init();
    </script>
<!--//end-animate-->
<!---webfonts-->
<link
href="//fonts.googleapis.com/css?family=Cabin:400,400italic,500,500italic,600,600italic,700,700italic"
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<!---//webfonts-->
<!-- Meters graphs -->
<script src="js/jquery-1.10.2.min.js"></script>
<!-- Placed js at the end of the document so the pages load faster -->

</head>

<body class="sticky-header left-side-collapsed" onload="initMap()">
    <section>
        <!-- left side start-->
            <div class="left-side sticky-left-side">

                <!--logo and iconic logo start-->
                <div class="logo">
                    <h1><a href="index.html">Easy <span>Admin</span></a></h1>
                </div>
                <div class="logo-icon text-center">
                    <a href="index.html"><i class="lnr lnr-home"></i> </a>

```

```

        </div>

        <!--logo and iconic logo end-->
        <div class="left-side-inner">

                <!--sidebar nav start-->
                <ul class="nav nav-pills nav-stacked custom-nav">
                        <li><a href="user_home.php"><i class="lnr lnr-
select"></i><span>Home</span></a></li>
                        <li>><a href="user_category.php"><i class="lnr lnr-
cog"></i> <span>Category</span></a></li>
                        <li><a href="user_income.php"><i class="lnr lnr-
pencil"></i> <span>Income</span></a></li>
                        <li><a href="user_expense.php"><i class="lnr lnr-
indent-increase"></i> <span>Expense</span></a></li>
                        <li class="active"><a href="user_view.php"><i
class="lnr lnr-eye"></i> <span>View</span></a></li>
                        <li><a href="user_report.php"><i class="lnr lnr-
book"></i> <span>Report</span></a></li>
                        <li><a href="index.php"><i class="lnr lnr-power-
switch"></i> <span>Logout</span></a></li>
                </ul>
                <!--sidebar nav end-->
        </div>
</div>
<!-- left side end-->

<!-- main content start-->
<div class="main-content">
        <!-- header-starts -->
        <div class="header-section">

                <!--toggle button start-->
                <a class="toggle-btn menu-collapsed"><i class="fa fa-bars"></i></a>

```

```

<!--toggle button end-->

<!--notification menu start -->
<div class="menu-right">
    <div class="user-panel-top">
        <div class="profile_details">
            <ul>
                <li class="dropdown profile_details_drop">
                    <a href="#" class="dropdown-toggle"
data-toggle="dropdown" aria-expanded="false">
                        <div class="profile_img">
                            <span
style="background:url(images/user1.png) no-repeat center"> </span>
                            <div class="user-
name">
                                <p><?php echo
$e?><span>user</span></p>
                                </div>
                                <i class="lnr lnr-
chevron-down"></i>
                                <i class="lnr lnr-
chevron-up"></i>
                            <div
class="clearfix"></div>
                        </div>
                    </a>
                    <ul class="dropdown-menu drp-mnu">
                        <li> <a href="index.php"><i
class="fa fa-sign-out"></i> Logout</a> </li>
                    </ul>
                </li>
            </ul>
            <div class="clearfix"> </div>
        </div>
    </div>
</div>

```

```

        </div>

        </div>
    </div>
    <!--notification menu end -->
    </div>
<!-- //header-ends -->
    <div id="page-wrapper">
        <div class="graphs">
            <h3 class="blank1">Expense Details </h3>
            <div class="grid_3 grid_4">
                <div class="bs-example ">
                    <table class="table" >
                        <tbody>
                            <tr>
                                <td><h1 id="h1">&nbsp;</h1></td>
                                <td class="type-info"><div align="center">
                                    <h1>EXPENSE</h1>
                                </div></td>
                                <td class="type-info">&nbsp;</td>
                            </tr>
                            <tr>
                                <td>&nbsp;</td>
                                <td class="type-info"><table class="table">
                                    <thead>
                                        <tr>
                                            <th>#</th>
                                            <th>Date</th>
                                            <th>Month</th>
                                            <th>Category</th>
                                            <th>Amount</th>
                                        </tr>
                                    </thead>
                                </table>
                            </td>
                        </tbody>
                    </table>
                </div>
            </div>
        </div>
    </div>

```

```

  <?php
      $a=1;
      while($row=mysql_fetch_array($xyz))
      {
          $b=$a%2;
          if($b==0)
          {
              ?>
  <tr class="info">
    <?php
      <th scope="row"><?php echo $a; ?></th>
      <td><?php echo $row['cdate'];?></td>
      <td><?php echo $row['month'];?></td>
      <td><?php echo $row['category'];?></td>
      <td><?php echo $row['amount'];
          $total= $total+$row['amount'];
          ?></td>
    </tr>
    <?php
      $a++;
      }
    ?>
      <tr >
        <th scope="row">&nbsp;</th>
        <td>&nbsp;</td>
        <td>&nbsp;</td>
        <td>&nbsp;</td>
        <td>&nbsp;</td>

```

```

        </tr>
        <tr class="danger">
            <th scope="row">&nbsp;</th>
            <td>&nbsp;</td>
            <td>&nbsp;</td>
            <td>Total Expense </td>
            <td><?php echo $total;?>&nbsp;</td>
        </tr>

        <tr class="danger">
            <th scope="row">&nbsp;</th>
            <td>&nbsp;</td>
            <td>&nbsp;</td>
            <td>Total Income </td>
            <td><?php echo $income;?>&nbsp;</td>
        </tr>

        <tr class="danger">
            <th scope="row">&nbsp;</th>
            <td>&nbsp;</td>
            <td>&nbsp;</td>
            <td>Balance</td>
            <td><?php
                $a=$income-$total;
                echo $a;

            ?>&nbsp;</td>
        </tr>
    </tbody>
</table></td>

        <td class="type-info">&nbsp;</td>
    </tr>
</tbody>
</table>
</div>
</div>

```

```

        </div>
        <div class="graphs">
<div class="col_3">
  <div class="col-md-3 widget widget1">
    <div class="r3_counter_box"> <i class="fa fa-mail-forward"></i>
      <div class="stats">
        <h5><?php
                                echo $income;

                                ?> <span>${</span></h5>

        <div class="grow">
          <p>Amount</p>
        </div>
      </div>
    </div>
  </div>
</div>
<div class="col-md-3 widget widget1">
  <div class="r3_counter_box"> <i class="fa fa-users"></i>
    <div class="stats">
      <h5>
        100
      <span>%</span></h5>
      <div class="grow grow1">
        <p>Income</p>
      </div>
    </div>
  </div>
</div>
<div class="col-md-3 widget widget1">
  <div class="r3_counter_box"> <i class="fa fa-eye"></i>
    <div class="stats">
      <h5>

```

```

        <?php
            echo $exp=($total/$income)*100;

        ?>

    <span>%</span></h5>
    <div class="grow grow3">
        <p>Expense</p>
    </div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
<div class="col-md-3 widget">
    <div class="r3_counter_box"> <i class="fa fa-usd"></i>
        <div class="stats">
            <h5>
                <?php
                    echo $profit=100-$exp;

                ?>

            <span>%</span></h5>
            <div class="grow grow2">
                <p>Profit</p>
            </div>
        </div>
    </div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
<div class="clearfix"> </div>
</div>
        <!-- switches -->
    <div class="switches">

```

```
<div class="col-4"></div>
</div>
      <!-- //switches -->
</div>
      </div>
    </div>
    <!--footer section start-->
      <footer>
        <p>&copy; 2019 Easy Admin Panel. All Rights Reserved | Design by
Admin.</a></p>
      </footer>
    <!--footer section end-->
  </section>

<script src="js/jquery.nicescroll.js"></script>
<script src="js/scripts.js"></script>
<!-- Bootstrap Core JavaScript -->
  <script src="js/bootstrap.min.js"></script>
</body>
</html>
```

8.2 O/P SCREENS

192.168.0.7 says
Register Successfully..

OK

Processing request...

192.168.0.7 says
Login Successfully

OK

Processing request...

The dashboard features a vertical sidebar on the left with icons for home, settings, edit, list, eye, mobile, and refresh. The main content area contains four cards: 'AMOUNT' with a green arrow icon and '0 \$', 'INCOME' with a blue group icon and '100 %', 'EXPENSE' with a red eye icon and a warning message, and 'PROFIT' with a yellow dollar sign icon and '100 %'. The warning message reads: 'Warning: Division by zero in C:\wamp\www\l on line 172 0 %'. At the bottom, there is a copyright notice: '© 2019 Easy Admin Panel. All Rights Reserved | Design by admin.'

The 'Expense Category' form is displayed within the same sidebar. It has a title 'Expense Category' and a main heading 'ADD NEW CATEGORY'. The form includes a 'Category' label with an input field containing the text 'travel', a 'Submit' button, and a 'Keywords' label with an empty input field. At the bottom, there is a copyright notice: '© 2019 Easy Admin Panel. All Rights Reserved | Design by Admin.'

Expense Category

ADD NEW CATEGORY

Category

#	Keywords
1	travel

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USER INCOME DETAILS

ADD INCOME

Amount

Month

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USER EXPENSE DETAILS

ADD EXPENSE

Month

Category

Amount

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Expense Details

EXPENSE

View

#	Date	Month	Category	Amount
1	20	11	travel	150
Total Expense				150
Total Income				50000
Balance				49850

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Expense Details

EXPENSE REPORT

Month

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Expense Details

EXPENSE

#	Date	Month	Category	Amount
1	20	1	travel	500

Total Expense	500
Total Income	10000
Balance	9500

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- Home
- Category
- Income
- Expense
- View
- Report
- Logout

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